

An Assessment of Information-Seeking Behaviour of Postgraduate Students in the Faculty of Education, University of Ibadan.

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Abstract

The study focused on information-seeking behaviour of postgraduate students in the faculty of education, University of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. Descriptive research was used for the study and the questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. The total population of the study comprised 1,703 postgraduate students from the faculty of education, University of Ibadan. Simple random sampling techniques were used and 20% of postgraduate students were selected which comprised 342 students. The questionnaire was analysed using simple frequency tables, percentages, mean and standard deviation for research questions. The findings of the study revealed that lecture notes and handouts, school library, using the Internet, consulting and photocopying colleagues' notes, textbooks, thesis/dissertations, print journals, research articles, review articles, research reports and seminars are the major sources of information available to postgraduate students of faculty of education, University of Ibadan. The findings of the study also revealed that the majority of the postgraduate students from the faculty of education seek information through the Internet.

Keywords: Information, information-seeking, information-seeking behaviour, postgraduate students, University of Ibadan

Introduction

For some decades, human beings have been seeking, organising, and using information as they learned and evolved patterns of human information behaviour for resolving problems related to survival, work and everyday life (Case, 2002). Information is a major ingredient that supports decision making, while reducing the degree of uncertainty. Information and its use are as old as man. Indeed, without information, there cannot be communication, (Olatokunbo and Asiru, 2011). Information can be written document or oral. Information resources are those materials which provide information for learning, teaching and research such as books, journals, encyclopaedias, films or pictures. According to Ingwersen and Jarvelin (2005), information behaviour is defined as the human behaviour dealing with generation, communication, use and other activities concerned with information, such as, information-seeking behaviour and information retrieval. This definition comprises all aspects of human behaviour that require

users to generate, source and seek for information that is relevant to their information needs. Information behaviour is becoming a fundamental and strategic aspect of intelligent citizenship. For students, understanding information behaviour helps to support information systems design and enhance the strategic planning of learning materials and their academic performance.

For postgraduate students, it is increasingly important to be “information literate.” An information literate person recognises the need for information, and knows how to search, evaluate and use what is found effectively. It is a crucial part of their daily lives. For information professionals, this ability helps them in the design and delivery of information in many different contexts. Understanding information behaviour patterns and the factors that affect them, will help in the identification and removal of obstacles to information use (Manmart, 2012). Engagement in behaviours like information avoidance and sense-making. Information behaviour describes how people need, seek, manage, give and use information in different contexts (Pettigrew, Fidel & Bruce, 2001). It is often also described as human information behaviour. An individual’s information behaviour is governed by the convictions of both what is relevant and meaningful in the environment and what will support a normative life (Pettigrew et al., 2001) and for most people, most of the time, information-related behaviour.

Information behaviour can be described as an individual’s manner of gathering and sourcing information for personal use, knowledge updating and development. Kakai, Ikoja-Odongo and Kigongo-Bukenya (2004), see information behaviour as the way people go about searching for information and how they react to it. They posited further that students’ information seeking behaviour involves purposeful information seeking as a result of the need to complete course assignments, prepare for class discussions, seminars, workshops, and write final-year research papers. Taylor (2000) surmised that the information sources (e.g. the library) that a user actually needs may not eventually tally with what is practically available, due to constraints either in the stock or the user’s own inability. Kakai, Ikoja-Odongo and Kigongo-Bukenya (2004) in their study observed that most students concentrate on using particular materials recommended by either their lecturers or colleagues who have used them before, rather than searching to find the most appropriate document to use. Information seeking which is a subset of information behaviour is the purposive seeking of information as a consequence of a need to satisfy some goal which an individual might have set for him/herself. In the course of seeking, the individual may interact with manual information systems such as a newspaper, magazine or a library, or with computer-based systems such as the Web. Information seeking behaviour involves personal reasons for seeking information, the kinds of information which are being sought, and the ways and sources with which needed information is being sought. Information behaviour could be expressed in various forms, from reading printed material to research and experimentation. Students and scholars actively seek current information from the various media available in their school libraries, e.g. encyclopaedias, journals and more currently, electronic media.

Information behaviour is a basic activity indulged in by all people and manifested through a particular way they act. It is also an aspect of scholarly work most interesting to academic librarians who strive to develop collections, services, and organizational structures that facilitate seeking of information (Wiberley, 1989 as cited in Adetola, 2016). There is a universal assumption that man was born innocent and should actively seek knowledge. 'Information seeking is thus a natural and necessary mechanism of human existence' (Marchionini, 1995). Information need which is also a subset of information behaviour is a factual situation in which, there exists an inseparable interconnection with "information" and "need", information needs can therefore be said to be the amount of positive information a students or group of users need to have for their work in school most especially assignment and examination, recreation and many other like satisfactions. Thus, information need arise wherever students find themselves in a situation requiring knowledge to deal with the situation as they deem fit. In other words, lack of information needed to accomplish a task results in information need which several authors have variously described and explained has actually hindered the performance of some students in their academic work (Fiankor and Adams, 2004; Adeniyi, 2007). Most times student's information behaviour involves active or purposeful information-seeking as a result of the need to complete course assignments, prepare for class discussions, seminars, workshops, conferences, or write final year research papers.

In the course of seeking and using information for learning, students are subject to a set of complex influences ranging from personal to environmental. These issues are compounded by the proliferation of information and communication and technology (ICT) in higher education and the emergence of digital information resources. Consequently, research in the area of information-seeking focuses on the factors which might have an influence on the behaviour of graduate students. These factors include information literacy, disciplinary area, the role of academics and the impact of accessibility of various types of information resources (Al-Muomen, 2012). Further, as cited in Wickramanayake (2010), Wilson mentions, 'information behaviour is closely related to user studies, market analysis, user surveys, information analysis, community analysis and information needs assessment that are widely applied in the study of user needs in library and information science'.

Statement of the problem

Research indicates that in most cases, the universities setting especially in Nigeria, students most especially postgraduates make increasing use of electronic resources but retain a preference for print materials and informal sources of information. These students face major barriers to information behaviour which may be different from those faced by their counterparts in Western countries. These include limited availability of resources, especially full text resources and poor Internet connection speeds or Internet availability, poor power supply among others. This situation is against the backdrop that modern modes of technology have changed the information environment in which students engage in their academic activities. Thus, increased knowledge of the different aspects of information behaviours of postgraduates

in the university is crucial to meeting their information needs. An academic institution where there is no availability of internet could affect the information behaviour of students in that they would find it difficult to access information the required information as this could affect the way they react to non-availability of such information. Furthermore, despite all frantic effort made by students to get the required information, power supply is a hindrance, in which lack of power could have effect on the availability of the Internet within the school, as this could debar postgraduates to access information, they need for their research work. Such students could act insouciantly towards their academic work and every other related academic activity.

Furthermore, studies have shown that various reasons could be accountable in impinging on the information behaviour of students. Some are of the opinion that libraries do not provide the necessary services they needed, why others are of the notion that postgraduate's information behaviour is influenced by demographic factors like their age, gender, income level, discipline variation, and internet access competence provided for in their various university libraries. In addition, extant literature seems to provide little information on studies that have been carried out on demographic, institutional factors and information behaviour of postgraduates in Nigeria, irrespective of the fact that studies have been done on other factors that play important role in the information behaviour of students. In the light of this, the present study investigates the demographics, institutional factors and information behaviour of faculty of Education postgraduate students of University of Ibadan.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to examine the information behaviour of faculty of education postgraduate students in the University of Ibadan.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. Find out the information behaviour of postgraduate students of faculty of education University of Ibadan;
- ii. Find out information sources available to postgraduate students of faculty of Education University of Ibadan.

Research questions

1. What is the information seeking behaviours of postgraduate students of faculty of education, University of Ibadan?
2. What are the various information sources available to postgraduate students of faculty of Education University of Ibadan?

Literature Review

Information behaviour of postgraduate students

Information is the most significant element of information-seeking behaviour and has been defined by various authors globally. Cawkell (2003) believes that 'Information is an assemblage of data in a comprehensible form capable of communication and use'. While as Martin (1995) believes Information is that which adds to or modifies knowledge structure. Information has been defined in several ways by different authors because the word information covers a lot of things. It is also defined by Rafael and Binger (2003) as the process of knowledge transformation, and particularly to selection and interpretation within a specific context. Also, using information and in turn increasing knowledge is a transitional process from distressing ignorance to becoming informed (Wellstand, 2011). Bates (2005) states Information behaviour is a broad term covering all aspects of information-seeking, including passive or undetermined information behaviour. Information-seeking behaviour is usually thought of as active or conscious information behaviour. Information-searching behaviour describes the interactive elements between a user and an information system. Gray (2003) states that research into information-seeking behaviour occupies a niche at the intersection of psychology, management, communications, and information science. Meho and Haas (2001) are of the view that information-seeking behaviour is a broad term that encompasses the way in which individuals articulate their information needs and seek, evaluate, and use information.

Information behaviour focuses on people's information needs; on how they seek, manage, give, and use information, both purposefully and passively, in the varied roles that comprise their everyday lives (Heidi, 2009). Wilson (2008) defines information behaviour as the totality of human behaviour in relation to sources and channels of information, including both active and passive information seeking and information use. Thorsteinsdottir (2001) put forward some other related concept to information behaviour. He asserted that information behaviour is intertwined concepts which make the concept information behaviour very complex. The concept the author gave are:

Information Needs: This is understanding in information science as stemming from a vague awareness of something missing and as culminating in locating information that contributes to understanding and meaning (Kuhlthau, 2013). It is an anomalous state of knowledge (Belkin, Brooks and Oddy, 2002), or a gap in individual's knowledge in sense making situations (Dervin and Nilan, 2006).

Information Seeking: Ikoja-Odongo and Ocholla (2004) described information seeking as a process that requires an information seeker, or what might be called 'personal information structures' 'such as a person's cognitive abilities, his or her knowledge, skills in relation to the problem or task domain, knowledge and skills specific to a system and knowledge and skills regarding information seeking. This activity may be actively or passively done. An information need arises when an individual sense a problematic situation or information gap, in which his or her internal knowledge and beliefs, and model of the environment fail to suggest a path towards the satisfaction of his or her goals (Case 2007).

Osiobe (2008) stated that browsing through Journals was the most important source of finding references for undergraduates' students. Osiobe (2008) found that browsing was the most important source of finding references for undergraduate students. The author concluded that respondents in the University of Botswana did seek help from University library staff with 40% receiving help from the reference librarian and approximately 32% from the subject librarian.

Owalabi, Jimoh and Okpeh (2010) in their study of information seeking behaviour of polytechnic students discovered that 285 (59.4%) of their respondents needs information in relation to their academic. It shows that students use information primarily for academic purposes. The study concluded that students at the polytechnic seek information to improve their academic performance. In a different study carried out by Fatima and Ahmad (2008), the findings show that 30 (50%) of the respondents seeks information on career development and other reason include seeking information for problem solving, keeping up-to-date and the need to write an article or research paper.

The study of Ajiboye and Tella (2007) conducted on university undergraduate's information seeking behaviour show that 12% of the respondents (students) required information for their personal development, while 11.25% claimed that they sought for information on health matter, and 64.1% sought for information for their academic development, 9.3% seeks information to secures employment. Also, Bhatti (2010) using faculty members at the Islamia University of Bahawalpur, respondents indicated their purposes of seeking information eighty-eight percent sought information for teaching purpose (preparing class lectures), 68 percent for literature searches, 43 percent to borrow books or journal articles, fifty-four percent of faculty members consult the library for research and 43 percent for keeping their knowledge up to date, and 27 percent visit the library for reading newspapers and magazines (recreational purposes). This clearly show that nearly all the respondents use library resources or seek for information for teaching with more than half seeking for research and a smaller number for various other purposes.

Tidings (2004) in her empirical research on information needs and seeking behaviour of library users reveals that greater percentage of the respondents usually seek for information concerning their course. To her, this is not unexpected because the quest for certificate in their respective field of study forms their primary aim of being in the college. Majid and Ai (2002) studied the use of information resources by computer engineering students in Singapore and found that the top five information resources in order of preference were books, (94%), Lecturers (84%), the internet (86%), and friends (84%). They relied heavily on printed sources of information and their use of electronic journals and databases was very low.

The research on information seeking behaviour of postgraduate students is bounteous. However, the paucity of similar studies in Nigerian Universities revealed a research gap that this study set out to fill.

Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive research. The targeted population for the study is all masters students in faculty of education, University of Ibadan, Oyo State. The total population of postgraduate students

(Masters) in faculty of education in University of Ibadan was 1,703. Simple random sampling techniques was used to select the postgraduate students (Masters) from faculty of education. In order to get the sample size, a sampling fraction of 20% was used to select the sample size from each of the Department. This therefore gives a total of 342.

Table 1 Sample size of the study

Departments	Number of Postgraduates	Sample Size
Adult Education	127	25
Arts and Social Sciences Education	74	15
Centre for Educational Media Resource Studies	54	11
Early Childhood and Educational Foundations	125	25
Educational Management	220	44
Guidance and Counselling	303	61
Human Kinetics and Health Education	99	20
Library, Archival and Information Studies	145	29
Science and Technology Education	65	13
Social Work	115	23
Special Education	122	24
Teacher Education	253	51
Institute of Education	1	1
Total	1,703	342

Source: University of Ibadan MIS 2016/2017 and 2017/2018 sessions

The questionnaire instrument was used for the study due to the high literacy level of the study population and also considering the nature of the data, the research design, analyses required, number of respondents and their dispersion time. The data collected were analysed and also tabulated using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Specifically, frequency tables, percentages, mean and standard deviation were used.

Table 2 Distribution of respondents by Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20-24 years	58	17.0
25-29 years	125	36.5
30-34 years	105	30.7
35-39 years	26	7.6
40 years and above	28	8.2
Total	342	100

Result from Table 2 reveals the ages of the respondents. 58 (17%) fell between 20-24 years, 125 (36.5%) fell between 25-29 years. 105 (30.7%) fell between 30-34 years while 26 (7.6%) fell between 35-39 years and the rest 28 (8.2%) fell between 40 years and above. This means that respondents whose age fell between 25-29 years participated more in the study than their other counterparts.

Table 3 Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	159	46.5
Female	183	53.5
Total	342	100

Table 3 shows the distribution of respondents by gender. Of the 324 respondents, 159 (46.5%) were males while 183 (53.5%) were females. This means that more female participated in the study than their male counterparts.

Table 4. What is the information seeking behaviour of Postgraduate students of Faculty of education (Masters) in University of Ibadan?

S/N	Information seeking behaviour	Frequency	Percentage
1.	I ask my colleagues	50	14.6%
2.	I get the information I desire by using catalogue cabinet	30	8.8%
3.	I ask from librarian	100	29.2%
4.	I use the internet	162	47.4%
	Total	342	100

The analysis of table 4 on the information seeking behaviour shows that I use Internet which ranked highest with 162(47.4%), this was followed by I ask librarian with 100(29.2%), "I ask my colleagues with 50(14.6%), while I get the information I desire by using catalogue cabinet ranked lowest 30(8.8%). Thus, majority of the postgraduate students seek information through the Internet

Question 6: What are the various information sources available to faculty of education postgraduates of University of Ibadan?

This research question was designed to examine the various information sources available to faculty of education postgraduates of University of Ibadan Some questionnaire items were employed to answer the research question four.

Table 6: Summary of various information sources available to postgraduates

	Sources of information	Yes	To some extent	No	Mean	SD
1	Lecture Notes & Handout	235 (68.7%)	99 (28.9%)	8 (2.3%)	1.3363	.5204
2	School Library	187 (54.7%)	121 (35.4%)	34 (9.9%)	1.5526	.6689
3	Internet	301 (88%)	13 (3.8%)	28 (8.2%)	1.2018	.5707
4	Consulting and photocopy colleagues' notes	170 (49.7%)	115 (33.6%)	57 (16.7%)	1.6696	.7458
5	University Bookshop	127 (37.1%)	150 (43.9%)	65 (19%)	1.8187	.7281
6	Textbooks	250 (73.1%)	92 (26.9%)	-	1.2690	.4441

7	Thesis/Dissertations	141 (41.2%)	154 (45%)	47 (13.7%)	1.7251	.6896
8	Newspaper	63 (18.4%)	160 (46.8%)	119 (34.8%)	2.1637	.7119
9	CD-ROMs Database	81 (23.7%)	97 (28.4%)	164 (48%)	2.2427	.8120
10	Print Journals	143 (23.7%)	168 (49.1%)	31 (9.1%)	1.6725	.6346
11	Electronic Resources	150 (43.9%)	182 (53.2%)	10 (2.9%)	1.5906	.5488
12	Encyclopedias	116 (33.9%)	173 (50.6%)	53 (15.5%)	1.8158	.6794
13	Research Articles	214 (62.6%)	116 (33.9%)	12 (3.5%)	1.4094	.5594
14	Review Articles	170 (49.7%)	122 (35.7%)	50 (14.6%)	1.6491	.7223
15	Abstracting and Indexing Sources	73 (21.3%)	177 (51.8%)	92 (26.9%)	2.0556	.6934
16	Conference Abstracts & Proceedings	56 (16.4%)	181 (52.9%)	105 (30.7%)	2.1433	.6719
17	Biographies	32 (9.4%)	186 (54.4%)	124 (36.3)	2.2690	.6204
18	Research reports	131 (38.3%)	162 (47.4%)	49 (14.3%)	1.7602	.6830
19	Seminar	196 (57.3%)	109 (31.9%)	37 (10.8%)	1.5351	.6830
20	Workshop	123 (36%)	154 (45%)	65 (19%)	1.8304	.7228
Average mean:		1.736				

Results of the various information sources available to faculty of education postgraduates of University of Ibadan are presented in Table 6. 235 (68.7%) claimed their sources of information is lecture notes and handout while 8 (2.3%) claimed no. 187 (54.7%) claimed school library while 34 (9.9%) claimed no. 301 (88%) claimed internet while 28 (8.2%) claimed no. Also, 170 (49.7%) claimed they Consult and photocopy colleagues notes while 57 (16.7%) claimed no. 127 (37.1%) claimed university bookshop while 65 (19%) claimed no. 250 (73.1%) claimed that their source of information is by consulting textbook while none claimed no. 141 (41.2%) claimed thesis/dissertations while 47 (13.7%) claimed no. 63 (18.4%) claimed newspapers while 119 (34.8%) claimed no.

Furthermore, 81 (23.7%) indicated CD-ROMs Database while 164 (48%) claimed no. 143 (23.7%) claimed print journals while 31 (9.1%) claimed no. 150 (43.9%) claimed electronic resources while 10 (2.9%) claimed no. 116 (33.9%) claimed encyclopaedias while 53 (15.5%) claimed no. 214 (62.6%) claimed research articles while 12 (3.5%) claimed no. 170 (49.7%) claimed review articles while 50 (14.6%) claimed no. 73 (21.3%) claimed Abstracting and Indexing Sources while 92 (26.9%) claimed no. In addition, 56 (16.4%) claimed Conference Abstracts & Proceedings while 105 (30.7%) claimed no. 32 (9.4%) claimed Biographies while 124 (36.3%) claimed no. 131 (38.3%) claimed Research reports while 49 (14.3%) claimed no. 196 (57.3%) claimed seminar while 37 (10.8%) claimed no. 123 (36%) claimed workshop while 65 (19%) claimed no. It could be concluded from the findings that the major information sources available to faculty of education postgraduate students of University of Ibadan are:

Lecture notes and handout, school library, Internet, consulting and photocopying colleagues' notes, textbooks, thesis/dissertations, print journals, research articles, review articles, research reports, workshop and seminar.

Discussion of the findings

What are the various information sources available to faculty of education postgraduate students of University of Ibadan?

The results on the various information sources available to faculty of Education postgraduate students of University of Ibadan revealed that Lecture notes and handout, school library, Internet, consulting and photocopying colleagues' notes, textbooks, thesis/dissertations, print journals, research articles, review articles, research reports and seminar are the major sources of information available to postgraduate students of University of Ibadan. The finding validates Hartmann (2011) who found that students experienced difficulty in locating items from the library collection and did not understand the processes for retrieving journal articles. Much earlier finding from Urquhart, (2006) also found that in spite the apparent predominance of the search engine and e-mail as part of sources of information behaviour, books are still considered a reliable, basic resources of information for students' academic work. Their study also showed that many students still turn to books as well as the Internet for routine academic queries, with books used first more frequently than the Internet. The finding also corroborates Osiobe (2008) who concluded that browsing was the most important source of finding references for undergraduate students. The author concluded that respondents in the University of Botswana did seek help from University library staff with 40% receiving help from the reference librarian and approximately 32% from the subject librarian.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is understood that information sources of postgraduate students of faculty of education, University of Ibadan are basically textbooks. Also, postgraduate students always use the internet to seek for their information needs. The successful operation of any library depends on her collection. The faculty of education library in University of Ibadan collection should meet up with the requirement of the postgraduate students.

Recommendation

1. Adequate power supply should be provided within the school as this would make students to be able to access information they would be needing as at when due. Alternative power supply such as inverter, solar, generating set etc. should be used to replace the electricity supply anytime there is power cut.

2. School management should ensure that Internet is available for use for students in their Department, Faculty and their various hall of residence as this would make them to have easy access to information that they would use to augment their study without any frustration.
3. The Department and Faculty libraries should be equipped with up-to-date books, and other materials that would make postgraduate students to have access to them when the need arises. Since postgraduate students are known to be researchers, if books and other materials are not available, they can be stressed and frustrated as this could hinder their academic interest.
4. Various information sources should be provided in the library with respect to the various needs of users within the academic community and such sources should be made known to users so as to increase the propensity of their search towards enhance the use of such information.

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